

Full conference name

Session Name

eventual DOI

© Authors. This work is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/)

Teaching and Training (TnT) and I'll win the Fight

Teaching and Training Research Data Management in Mathematics

Björn Schembera¹

¹Institute of Applied Analysis and Numerical Simulation, University of Stuttgart, Germany

²Universität Leipzig, Germany

³Max Planck Institute for Mathematics in the Sciences, Leipzig, Germany

*Correspondence: Björn Schembera, bjoern.schembera@mathematik.uni-stuttgart.de

Abstract

The Mathematical Research Data Initiative (MaRDI) is the only math-specific consortium inside the NFDI. MaRDI set itself the ambitious task to provide services and research data management (RDM) training for a very diverse community of researchers: some using pen and paper only to develop new theory, some using a supercomputer to run numerical simulations, and everything in between. At the start of MaRDI's funding period, RDM topics were rarely taught in mathematics departments and little known [1].

The consortium planned to tackle this situation by providing training through community workshops led by individual data-centered task areas, including computer algebra, scientific computing, statistics and machine learning, as well as cooperation with other disciplines and a general outreach team.

The resources created within MaRDI for the purpose of teaching and training in RDM include a math-specific one-semester interactive RDM class “Infrastructure for Mathematics” at the University of Leipzig [2] and a general, interdisciplinary RDM course at the University of Stuttgart [3]. In addition to these courses, a first prototype of a train-the-trainer was developed and presented at the Math meets Information Specialists Workshop¹ [4]. The MaRDI Station, available as a portable or exhibition version, offers a gamified approach to RDM topics, with a prototype launched for the Love Data Week 2024 [5]. The game enables the user to autonomously learn about pitfalls in RDM and the importance of proper data sharing.

In addition, an overview paper on the status quo of RDM planning in the German mathematics community [6] and a white paper on RDM Planning in Mathematics [7] has been published. MaRDI's outreach team runs a quarterly newsletter which introduces RDM topics and services to the community [8] and they reported on the success and focus of their activities, encouraging future trainers to “make it personal” and “make it fun” [9]. Together with experts in algebraic phylogenetics, MaRDI transformed the early 2000's database “Small Phylogenetic Trees” into a best-practice example of FAIR

¹<https://www.mis.mpg.de/events/series/vom-beweis-zum-bibliotheksregal-workshop-rund-um-forschungsdatenmanagement-fuer-die-mathematik>

mathematics, comprising a modern website and software package, as well as a report on lessons learned [10].

With the resources presented, we have created a solid, introductory-style foundation that we intend to adapt to other user groups in future work, for example to different areas of mathematics or for different career levels. We are also aiming for a modular approach, possibly as an addition to the FDM Mentor project [11].

Resources

- Infrastructure for Mathematics. <https://sites.google.com/view/goergen/teaching>. One-semester interactive RDM class “Infrastructure for Mathematics” at the University of Leipzig
- Schlüsselqualifikation Forschungsdatenmanagement. Ein Kurs in 8 Teilen. http://hdl.handle.net/10900.3/OER_EAXYKYZG. Interdisciplinary RDM course at the University of Stuttgart
- Train the Math-Trainer. <https://zenodo.org/records/15222157>. A training session that has been developed for potential trainers being assumed to have a degree in mathematics but no RDM knowledge
- Research Data Management Planning in Mathematics <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10018246>. Whitepaper to guide mathematicians and researchers from related disciplines who create research data management (RDM) plans.
- MaRDI Newsletter and community page <https://www.mardi4nfdi.de/community/start-here>. A low-level entry point to RDM topics in mathematics.

Author contributions

Christiane Görgen: Conceptualization, Resources, Writing – original draft. Björn Schembera: Conceptualization, Resources, Writing – original draft. Both authors contributed equally.

Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

Funding

Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG), Projektnummer 460135501. NFDI 29/1 “MaRDI – Mathematische Forschungsdateninitiative”

Acknowledgements

The authors are grateful to all participants of the workshops they hosted for fruitful discussions regarding training requirements. In particular, we wish to thank Anja Herwig und Daniela Hausen for their thorough feedback on our first train the trainer draft.

References

- [1] D. Clauss and V. Reiter, “Der Onlinekurs ‘Gute wissenschaftliche Praxis’,” *Mitteilungen der Deutschen Mathematiker-Vereinigung*, vol. 29, no. 4, pp. 243–245, 2021. DOI: [doi: 10.1515/dmvm-2021-0086](https://doi.org/10.1515/dmvm-2021-0086). [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.1515/dmvm-2021-0086>.
- [2] C. Görgen. “Infrastructure for mathematics.” Lecture notes and course material. (2025), [Online]. Available: <https://sites.google.com/view/goergen/teaching> (visited on 04/04/2025).
- [3] B. Schembera. “Schlüsselqualifikation Forschungsdatenmanagement. Ein Kurs in 8 Teilen.” Course Material for general RDM Teaching. (2024), [Online]. Available: http://hdl.handle.net/10900.3/OER_EAXYKYZG (visited on 04/09/2025).
- [4] C. Görgen and B. Schembera, *Train the trainer – Forschungsdatenmanagement in der Mathematik*, version 0.1, Apr. 2025. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.15222157](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15222157). [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15222157>.
- [5] MaRDI task area Data culture and community integration. Prototype of the MaRDI Station. (2024), [Online]. Available: <https://www.mardi4nfdi.de/community/love-data-week-2024> (visited on 04/04/2025).
- [6] T. Boege, R. Fritze, C. Görgen, *et al.*, “Data management planning in the German mathematical community,” *European Mathematical Society Magazine*, no. 130, pp. 40–47, 2023.
- [7] T. M. Consortium, *Research data management planning in mathematics*, Oct. 2023. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.10018246](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10018246). [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10018246>.
- [8] MaRDI task area Data culture and community integration. Series of Newsletter articles. (2021–2025), [Online]. Available: <https://www.mardi4nfdi.de/community/start-here> (visited on 04/04/2025).
- [9] T. Bacher, C. Görgen, T. Krause, A. Matt, D. Ramos, and B. Violet, “Spreading the love for mathematical research data,” *Proceedings of the Conference on Research Data Infrastructure*, vol. 1, Sep. 2023. DOI: [10.52825/cordi.v1i.369](https://doi.org/10.52825/cordi.v1i.369). [Online]. Available: <https://www.tib-op.org/ojs/index.php/CoRDI/article/view/369>.
- [10] T. Bacher, M. Garrote-López, C. Görgen, and M. Neubert, *Making mathematical online resources FAIR: At the example of small phylogenetic trees*, 2025. arXiv: [2501.10823](https://arxiv.org/abs/2501.10823) [math.HO]. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2501.10823>.
- [11] K. Biernacka, P. Buchholz, S. A. Danker, *et al.*, *Train-the-Trainer-Konzept zum Thema Forschungsdatenmanagement*. Zenodo, Dec. 2021. DOI: [10.5281/zenodo.5773203](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5773203). [Online]. Available: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5773203>.